

Neutrino cross sections: path toward precision

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Cross sections in accelerator neutrino physics

- Main goal: extract the ν & $\bar{\nu}$ oscillation probabilities, search for BSM physics.
- Polychromatic beams, neutrino energy reconstructed from visible energy deposited by interaction products.
- Accurate cross section in a Monte Carlo simulation essential to account for the missing energy, near-far flux differences, backgrounds etc.
- For example, in DUNE, the average energy in the near and far detector differs by 7% (2021 fluxes).
- Accuracy of simulations translates into the accuracy of the extracted oscillation parameters.
- Our goal is O (1%) accuracy.

Current situation

"... nuclear models available to modern neutrino experiments give similar results ... none of which is confirmed by the data. ... More theoretical work is needed to correctly model nuclear effects ... from the quasielastic to the deep inelastic regime."

B. G. Tice *et al.* (MINERvA), PRL 112, 231801 (2014)

"The double- and single-differential cross sections show similar tensions with the model predictions. These results demonstrate that **improvements will need to be made to neutrino-interaction models if precision neutrino oscillation experiments hope to better constrain the systematics ...**"

A. Filkins *et al.* (MINERvA), PRD 101, 112007 (2020)

Are neutrino data sufficient?

"... fitting to individual MINERvA pion production channels [$1\pi^\pm$ and $N\pi^\pm$ for ν_μ , and $1\pi^0$ for ν_μ and $\bar{\nu}_\mu$] produces **different best-fit parameters** ..."

"Because the four channels cover different kinematic regions and contain different physics, it is **difficult to pinpoint the origin of the discrepancy** ..."

"The main conclusion ... is that current **neutrino experiments** ... **should think critically about single pion production** models and uncertainties, as the Monte Carlo models which are currently widely used in the field are unable to explain multiple datasets, even when they are from a single experiment."

P. Stowell *et al.* (MINERvA), PRD 100, 072005 (2019)

Neutrino double differential cross section

A.M.A. & A. Friedland, PRD 102, 053001 (2020)

Neutrino double differential cross section

A.M.A. & A. Friedland, PRD 102, 053001 (2020)

Impulse approximation

At relevant kinematics, the dominant process of neutrino-nucleus interaction is **scattering off a single nucleon**, with the remaining nucleons acting as a spectator system.

This description is valid when the momentum transfer $|\mathbf{q}|$ is high enough ($|\mathbf{q}| \gtrsim 200$ MeV).

Impulse approximation

$$\frac{d\sigma_{\ell A}^{\text{IA}}}{d\omega d\Omega} = \sum_N \int d^3p dE P_{\text{hole}}^N(\mathbf{p}, E) \frac{M}{E_{\mathbf{p}}} \frac{d\sigma_{\ell N}^{\text{elem}}}{d\omega d\Omega} P_{\text{part}}^N(\mathbf{p}', \mathcal{T}')$$

average over the initial nucleon state

nucleon cross section

final-state interactions

Electrons and neutrinos

For scattering in a given angle and energy, ν 's and e 's differ almost exclusively due to the [elementary cross sections](#).

Comparing to electron-scattering data we are sensitive to any problems with

- the energy and momentum distributions of the nucleons bound in the target
- the vector part of the cross sections, channel by channel
- final-state interactions

[Global comparisons to electron-scattering data allow validation of cross-section models, and rigorous determination and reduction of their systematic uncertainties.](#)

White paper: A.M.A., A. Ashkenazi, S. Bacca, J. L. Barrow, M. Betancourt, A. Bodek, M. E Christy, L. Doria, S. Dytman, A. Friedland , O. Hen, C. J. Horowitz, N. Jachowicz , W. Ketchum, T. Lux *et al.*,
JPG 50, 120501 (2023)

D(e,e') in the Monte Carlo generator GENIE

Adopted from
A.M.A. & A. Friedland, PRD 102, 053001 (2020)

D(e,e') in the Monte Carlo generator GENIE

Adopted from
A.M.A. & A. Friedland, PRD 102, 053001 (2020)

Realistic description of $D(e, e')$

Pion production: Bosted & Christy,
PRC **77**, 065206 (2008); PRC **81**, 055213 (2010)

Electron scattering on carbon at low energies

data: Barreau *et al.*,
NPA 402, 515 (1983)

A.M.A. & Alex Friedland,
PRD 102, 053001 (2020)

Relevant for T2K/Hyper-K, SBND, etc.

Electron scattering on argon

data: Dai *et al.*,
PRC 99, 054608 (2019)

A.M.A. & A. Friedland,
PRD 102, 053001 (2020)

GENIE 3 update

2.12

A.M.A. & A. Friedland,
PRD 102, 053001 (2020)

3.2

A. Papadopoulou *et al.*, PRD 103, 113003 (2021)

Global Fermi gas

Nucleus treated as a fragment of non-interacting infinite nuclear matter of constant density.

Eigenstates have definite momenta and energies $E_p = \sqrt{M^2 + \mathbf{p}^2} - \epsilon$.

Coordinate space

Momentum space

Local Fermi gas

Nucleus treated as set of concentric spheres of varying density, each treated as the global Fermi gas

<http://discovery.phys.virginia.edu/research/groups/ncd/index.html>

Shell structure observed using KDAR ν 's

Marzec *et al.* (JSNS² Collaboration), PRL 134, 081801 (2025)

Shell structure

Amaldi *et al.*, PRL 13, 341 (1964)

In '70 in Saclay, coincidence measurements performed with 1-MeV energy resolution

Shell structure

Frascati experiment, energy resolution 10 MeV

Amaldi *et al.*, PRL 13, 341 (1964)

NIKHEF-K experiment, energy resolution 0.15 MeV

Van der Steenhoven *et al.*, NPA 480, 547 (1988)

Short-range correlations

At short distances, repulsive interactions between nucleons create NN pairs (typically pn) with high relative momenta, which can only be probed at large energy transfers. Their presence depletes shell-model states.

Lapikás, NPA 553, 297c (1993)

Short-range correlations

480 MeV, 36 deg
 ~ 284 MeV, 0.08 GeV²

Spectral function

A.M.A., O. Benhar & M. Sakuda, PRC 110, 054612 (2024)

Fermi gas vs. spectral function

A.M.A., O. Benhar & M. Sakuda, PRC 110, 054612 (2024)

Energy conservation

$$E_\nu + M_A = E_\mu + E_{A-1} + E_{p'}$$

$$E_\nu + M_A = E_\mu + E_{A-1} + E_{p'} + U_V(p')$$

Energy conservation

$$E_\nu + M_A = E_\mu + E_{A-1} + E_{p'}$$

$$E_\nu + M_A \approx E_\mu + E_{A-1} + E_{p'} + U_V(p')$$

Final-state interactions

- Soft interactions with the spectator system change the **energy spectrum** of the struck nucleon
 - can be described using the real part of the optical potential.

Interactions with the spectator system complicate energy conservation and **broaden the cross section**

- can be modeled in the convolution approach.
- When collisions happen, the struck nucleon may get absorbed and/or **additional nucleons** may appear in the final states
 - can be simulated using intranuclear cascade.

Realistic description of the nucleus: C(e,e')

480 MeV, 36 deg

~ 284 MeV, 0.08 GeV²

SF w/ FSI,
LDA treatment
of Pauli blocking

SF w/ FSI,
step function

RFG

SF w/o FSI

What is not included?

A.M.A., O. Benhar & M. Sakuda, PRD 91, 033005 (2015)

Realistic description of the nucleus: C(e, e')

A.M.A., O. Benhar & M. Sakuda, PRD 91, 033005 (2015)

Spectral function in NuWro 25.11

data: Barreau *et al.*,
NPA 402, 515 (1983)

data: Sealock *et al.*,
PRL 62, 1350 (1989)

A.M.A., R. Dharmapal Banerjee, J.T. Sobczyk, J. L. Bonilla, K.M. Graczyk, B.E. Kowal, Hemant Prasad
arxiv:2508.10101

NuWro 25.11: MicroBooNE CC2p0 π

data: Abratenko et al., arXiv:2211.03734

For more details, see the talk by Rwik on Thursday!

Spectral function in NEUT 5.9

data: Barreau *et al.*,
NPA 402, 515 (1983)

S. Abe,
PRD 111, 033006 (2025)

Spectral function in (a future) GENIE

Betancourt *et al.*,
PRD 108, 113009 (2023)

Summary

- The success of the long-baseline neutrino program requires substantial progress in accuracy and precision of neutrino-nucleus cross sections.
- Comparisons to electron data covering the whole relevant kinematics are essential to validate the employed models and rigorously determine their systematic uncertainties.
- Great deal of progress in the quasielastic channel, across all Monte Carlo generators.
- Main challenge ahead remains pion production, including final state interactions affecting the hadronic spectra.

Thank you!

Neutron energy contribution

A.M.A. *et al.*, PRD 92, 073014 (2015)

Electron scattering on carbon

Moniz *et al.*, PRL 26, 445 (1971)

How about other targets?

Whitney *et al.*, PRC 9, 2230 (1974)

How about other *kinematics*?

data: Barreau *et al.*, NPA 402, 515 (1983)

Fits of Bosted & Christy

P.E. Bosted and M.E. Christy, PRC 77, 065206 (2008)

M.E. Christy and P.E. Bosted, PRC 81, 055213 (2010)

- 3.5k points for H ($0 \leq Q^2 < 8 \text{ GeV}^2$, $1.1 < W < 3.1 \text{ GeV}$)
16.3k points for D ($0 \leq Q^2 < 10 \text{ GeV}^2$, $1.1 < W < 3.2 \text{ GeV}$)
- For D, the Paris wave function used to extract the free nucleon response functions
- Resonant and nonresonant contributions treated separately
- 7 resonances parametrized as a (Breit-Wigner in W^2) \times $A(Q^2)$, nonresonant as $f(W^2, Q^2)$
- Smooth transitions from resonance photoproduction to electroproduction, and to DIS

NEUT 5.9

- Updated spectral function implementation for QE interactions
S. Abe, PRD 111, 033006 (2025)
- Dynamical coupled-channels model for single pion production
H. Kamano, S. X. Nakamura, T.-S. H. Lee, and T. Sato, PRC 94, 015201 (2016)
- Bodek-Yang approach for deep inelastic scattering
A. Bodek and U. K. Yang, Nucl. Phys. B, Proc. Suppl. 112, 70 (2002).

C(e,e') in NEUT: FSI

data: Barreau *et al.*,
NPA 402, 515 (1983)

S. Abe,
PRD 111, 033006 (2025)

NuWro 25.11 in a nutshell

- Updated spectral function implementation for QE interactions, including a consistent treatment of correlated nucleons in the initial state

C. Ciofi degli Atti and S. Simula, Phys. Rev. C 53, 1689 (1996).

L. Jiang *et al.*, PRD 105, 112002 (2022); L. Jiang *et al.*, PRD 107, 012005 (2023)

[More details in the talk of Rwik Dharmapal Banerjee on Thursday!](#)

- Implementation of final state interactions (for inclusive and exclusive x-sections)

A. M. Ankowski., O. Benhar, and M. Sakuda, PRD 91, 033005 (2015)

[More details in the talk of Rwik Dharmapal Banerjee on Thursday!](#)

- Valencia 2020 to model MEC: exclusive final states

J. E. Sobczyk, J. Nieves, and F. Sánchez, PRC 102, 024601 (2020)

H. Prasad, J. T. Sobczyk, A. M. Ankowski, J. L. Bonilla, R. Dharmapal Banerjee, K. M. Graczyk, and B. E. Kowal, PRD 111, 036032 (2025)

- Ghent hybrid model for single pion production: inclusion of higher resonances

Q. Yan, K. Niewczas, A. Nikolakopoulos, R. González-Jiménez, N. Jachowicz, X. Lu, J. Sobczyk, and Y. Zheng, JHEP 12 (2024) 141

- Bodek-Yang approach for deep inelastic scattering

A. Bodek and U. K. Yang, Nucl. Phys. B, Proc. Suppl. 112, 70 (2002).